

APPLICATION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11080889>

Abstract. *In this article, the problems related to the application of modern technologies in the development of creative competence of the future primary school teacher are considered.*

Keywords: *modern technology, technology, components, categories, pedagogical research, usual talent, creativeness.*

Based on the development of creative competence, which is seen as the main stage of the process of training future primary school teachers in the world education system, scientific research is being carried out to improve the pedagogical skills of future specialists and improve their intellectual creative competence. The use of a creative approach in educational institutions in the development of creative competence, the creation of didactic support for the development of creative competence, and the development of professional and personal qualities based on innovative technologies, taking into account the requirements of the employer in the training of elementary school teachers, are directly related to the scientific solution.

The final and intermediate results of the independent educational activities of the future elementary school teachers are recorded in the preparation and presentation of creative products such as an essay, an open lesson, a speech at a scientific conference or a pedagogical council, a work program, didactic material, a methodical manual, and the publication of an article in a scientific-methodical magazine. will be done. The presence of intermediate positive results is one of the necessary elements of a creative person's life strategy. If the teacher perceives the final results achieved as an achievement, success, such results become a starting point for further creative growth.

The use of modern information technologies makes it possible to make independent educational activities more flexible and mobile within the framework of creative circle work. The Internet provides a wealth of opportunities for independent learning for future teachers.

Independent education is aimed at creative self-development of the teacher and activation of his internal personal resources. The goal of the independent educational activity of the future elementary school teacher is to achieve a new level of creative competence and professional skills. In the process of developing creative competence, the teacher is formed not only as a subject of professional activity, but also at the personal level. Differences and imbalances between the need and readiness to implement and organize creative activities encourage teachers to move to another aspect of creative independent education. Changing the teacher's inner world, changing its content and essence, realizing the need to search for new opportunities to show the creative abilities and possibilities of the teacher's personality in pedagogical activity is the main condition for the teacher's creative development. The richness, versatility and emotional intensity of educational activities motivate teachers to study themselves as a profession. In the process of pedagogical dialogue and professional development on the basis of additional professional educational

institutions, a creative teacher realizes that he has insufficiently developed professionally important characteristics and sets himself the goal of solving existing problems in independent educational activities. The teacher develops an independent educational program that defines the goals, tasks, stages and forms of activities that allow him to achieve the desired results. Psychologists believe that the development of a person takes place in the process of his own active action, which occurs only when the actions of a person are directed to a specific goal and internally based. The main mechanism of independent education as a purposeful influence on a person himself is to resolve conflicts between the defined characteristics and qualities of a person and the objective requirements of professional activity, to perform creative tasks that are constantly becoming more complicated.

In the process of professional activity, they express the mechanism of development: development is carried out by the force of external regulatory forces, the method of action determined by external factors, in the direction of conscious, undirected regulation. This understanding of the mechanism of professional self-development encourages us to study the pedagogical conditions that help and hinder the development of creative competence of future elementary school teachers. We will consider these issues in the next paragraph.

All-round development of a person, consisting of intellectual, physical, spiritual-ethical, labor and aesthetic development, is realized in independent educational activities. Mental development refers to the acquisition of knowledge, the development of worldviews and beliefs. Moral development is the education of positive personality traits in a person based on knowledge about the norms of behavior. Both in aesthetic development and in moral development, importance is attached to aesthetic education, mastery of knowledge in the field of art and special types of artistic creativity.

The developmental influence expressed in one or another quality of the person is manifested both directly and indirectly. In the process of independent education, connections are established between mental, physical, moral, labor and aesthetic development.

Social maturity is the period of active labor activity of a person in which the formation of a person as a subject of activity and creative possibilities are manifested. Creative activity is distinguished by its goal orientation to perform non-standard pedagogical activities. In the process of independent education, the teacher enters into creative relations with his colleagues, as a result of which he is formed as a subject of communication and a subject of knowledge. The professional activity of the future elementary school teacher affects the formation of the specific characteristics of the field of knowledge and, of course, the development of the necessary ability to see creatively in various pedagogical situations.

Therefore, the future elementary school teacher receives too much professional information from various sources of influence: special methodical literature, the Internet, printed sources, radio, television.

One stream of this information comes through channels organized for pedagogical purposes according to the educational level of groups of people.

Another flow of information reaches the future elementary school teacher through mass media and affects his independent educational activities. Both currents affect the teacher throughout his life and require to understand his world, to manage his perception (perception) from a pedagogical point of view.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. “Erkin va farovon, demokratik O’zbekiston davlatini mard va olijanob xalqimiz bilan birga quramiz” mavzusidagi O’zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti lavozimiga kirishish tantanali marosimiga bag’ishlangan Oliy Majlis palatalarining qo’shma majlisidagi nutqi. – T.: O’zbekiston, 2016. –13-14 b.
2. Sh.Sharipov, N.Muslimov, M.Ismoilova. “Kasbiy ta’lim pedagogikasi“. Metodik qo’llanma.- T.2005 y
3. N. Bayturayeva. Developing the creative competence of future primary school teacher as a social problem. International Vritual Conference On Innovative Thoughts, Research Ideas and Inventions in Sciences Hosted from Newyork, USA <http://euroasiaconference.com> January 20th 2021.